

Performance Evaluation of Pt. Kintetsu World Express to Delivery Performance System Container Round Use (CRU) Pt. Honda Trading Aloz that has an Impact on Customer Satisfaction in 2016-2019

Eko Sujatmiko¹, Dr. Ir. Edhie Budi Setiawan, MM.²; Dr. Ir. Richardianto Prasadja, MM.³
19C606001065¹

The Department of Transportation Management
Trisakti Institute of Transportation & Logistics DKI Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- Evaluation of service quality and operational performance during delivery process are determining factors toward customer satisfaction. As such, there are necessary efforts to increase delivery performance of container round use (CRU) system. The research was conducted in PT. Honda Trading Aloz with sample amounting to 114 employees. Data was gathered through instrument in form of questionnaire with tested Likert scale. The used data analysis method is path analysis. First research result found that service performance has positive and significant correlation towards delivery performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that operational performance has positive and significant correlation towards delivery performance. Relevant service and operational performance in delivery has effects to increase customer satisfaction, thus delivery performance as intervening variable is proved to improve service quality and operational performance towards customer satisfaction.

Keywords:- Service quality, operational performance, delivery performance, customer satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the use of the container round use (CRU) system, many things and permit requirements must be considered, such as adjusting the arrival time of the ship and also the departure of the ship must be adjusted to each other because this is very dependent on both import and export activities. This should always be considered in the process of adjusting ship schedules, ship destinations, stevedoring warehouse locations, which container will be used and also the handling of documents that will affect the smooth running of round use export and import activities, one of which shipping line company (shipping company) will be used for shipments that will use the container round use (CRU) system itself and the facilities available can support the speed of work and facilities support in the process of activity. Good, fast and accurate service in terms of handling container round use (CRU) systems in export and import activities is very influential for PT. Kintetsu World Express Indonesia i.e. PT. Honda Trading Aloz in order to gain trust in the field of cargo delivery services so that it can win the competition among similar service companies. Service quality is the performance of a product or service that can meet the needs or even exceed customer expectations not only once but

repeatedly so as to provide satisfaction, thus service quality is the fulfilment of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibility provided to customers (Waluyo, 2018). By implementing a handling system for regular and integrated container round use (CRU) activities, in order to achieve smooth flow of export and import activities.

Looking at the customer request of PT. Honda Trading Aloz whose delivery schedule is erratic and always increasing, PT. Kintetsu World Express Indonesia must have a planning analysis on export and import container delivery activities, such as the readiness of export and import customer service performance in establishing good communication with customers on container delivery schedules and adjusting the schedule owned by the Shipping line (shipping company) to ATA Actual Time Arrival (arrival time) and ETD Estimated Time Departure (departure time) of ships, Operational Performance Readiness as a supervision of the process of loading / unloading activities at ports and in loading / unloading warehouses, availability of trucks to be used, readiness of goods to be exported. So PT. Kintetsu World Express Indonesia must be wise in offering products to all customers so that the export and import delivery process is in accordance with the target and carries out the delivery process on time according to customer requests and adjustments to ship schedules and export and import activities.

However, the use of container round use (CRU) has obstacles in export and import activities. These obstacles are having to compile in estimated data in the form of ETA (estimated time of arrival), ATA (arrival time), ship schedule against ETD Estimated Time Departure (departure time) that will be used to the destination country, on the ship's escort there are some problems that are owned that there are some late ship schedules because the ship must be aware in several other destination countries and there are delays during the cargo transit process. See whether the ship has a destination according to the cargo that will be sent according to the customer's destination request because some shipping line companies do not all have destinations to the countries that the customer wants. lack of communication between export import customer service to customers about the readiness of goods to be loaded in the warehouse of PT. Honda Trading Indonesia. Determine which container will be used and the destination of the ship,

determine which shipping line company has a contract with PT. Kintetsu World express Indonesia and has a low purchase price to reduce shipping costs, determine the trucking vendor to be used has a fairly cheap rental price and the best service, delays in the administrative process of documents that will be used as licensing requirements in the import and export process approved by Customs as a government agency in charge of providing approval for goods entering / leaving the country of Indonesia.

The phenomenon in the development of freight forwarding companies has consumers who can be classified in the form of individuals or in the form of companies that routinely ship goods using the services of freight forwarding companies, these consumers are very variant in their services, ranging from the fastest to still concentrating containers in container yards. This phenomenon will bring up various perceptions between hope and reality to be achieved. It will even have an impact on the release of communication and recommendations to other potential customers. Based on the above phenomenon, the urgency that becomes the goal of consumers as customers contained in previous research of property (Ratnasari, 2015) is the suitability of costs incurred as a form of sacrifice and expected service.

In this case, the shipment handling of PT. Honda Trading Indonesia in container round use (CRU) delivery activities has differences in the activities carried out by export import customer service and operational employees of PT. Kintetsu World Express Indonesia is compared to dry container delivery process activities. Therefore, shipment activities with export and import round use (CRU) container delivery products can be said to be less than optimal services provided to customers because the results of these services affect the satisfaction obtained by customers.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

This research attempts to said the following questions:

- How does the quality of export import customer service directly affect delivery performance?
- How does the performance of the operational division directly affect Delivery Performance?
- How does the quality of export import customer service directly affect customer satisfaction?
- How the performance of the import-export operations division directly affects customer satisfaction?
- How does performance delivery directly affect customer satisfaction?
- Is there an indirect effect of import-export service quality on customer satisfaction through delivery performance?
- Is there an indirect influence of operational performance on customer satisfaction through delivery performance?

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Logistics Management

Logistics is "everything or objects that are tangible and can be treated physically, both used to carry out the main activities and supporting activities in an organization" (Donald J. Bowersox, 2006).

From the explanation above, Logistics is a series of planning, organizing, supervising procurement activities.

B. Receiving dan Delivery

According to (Lasse, 2012), receiving and delivery activities are the last series or activities in dock operations (bertboperation) and are an important link between ports and importers and exporters in the back area (binterland). Of the four activities in the dock activity, this activity is the most difficult to control, because the success of operations does not solely depend on the port manager himself, but there are other related parties such as transportation operators, freight forwarding, ADPEL (Shipping Administration), Customs and Cakai, and other security parties at the port. While outside the port there are also parties that determine the success of this operation such as providing good transportation access such as roads, railways, and inland rivers.

According to (Lasse, 2012) receiving/delivery is the work of moving goods from the stockpile/stacking place in the warehouse/stacking field and handing over until it is arranged on top of the vehicle at the warehouse door/stacking field or vice versa.

From the definition of receiving and delivery activities is an activity of receiving and delivering goods that takes place on the side of the hull or dock or in the stacking field, and can also be carried out in a closed stacking field area (warehouse) or vice versa.

According to (Lasse, 2012) In receiving and delivery activities, two types of activities are known as follows:

➤ Direct Operation

The direct operation load is the handover and acceptance taking place on the dock side, The activities in direct operations are as follows:

- Transport vehicles are called or come on the side of the ship or dock.
- The cargo is mounted on the conveyance and loaded onto the ship.
- The empty vehicle immediately moves up the dock and to the location of the document settlement.

➤ Indirect Operations

Indirect route loads are handover or receiving operations that take place on the land side of warehouse doors or stacking yards. The indirect activities include the following:

- Placement of land transport vehicles on the loading line in transit warehouses or at handover points in stacking fields.
- Transfer of cargo between vehicles and stacking or vice versa from stacking to vehicle.
- Completion of the document procedure, then the vehicle leaves the place of accumulation.

C. Quality of Service

According to (Waluyo, 2018) Quality is the extent to which product meets its specs, The quality of service is the performance of a product or service that can meet needs or even exceeds the customer's expectations not just once but repeatedly so as to provide satisfaction, then customer perceptions obtained from such products or services have a quality.

According to (Fandi, 2011) customer values not only include quality, but also the price. A certain service may have superior qualities, but evaluated as a low value because it's too expensive. As with customer satisfaction and quality service, customer value concept is still in its early stages. One of the sizes developed for evaluating customer values is *perval* (perceived value). Besides, The customer value measurements can also be based on the top three customer roles in the purchase decision, that's the user's value, The buyer's value, and the taxpayer's grades.

According to Hanif Mauludin (2004) in journal quotes (Winoto et al., 2016) define the quality of service as a result of perception and comparison between customer hope and true service performance. According to the plan, there are two major factors that affect the quality of service: expected service (expected service) and perceived service (received service).

Thus the quality of service is the fulfillment of the dimensional quality of service that can be judged by, Physical evidence, reliability, Responsiveness, and empathy. provided to customers. Every organization will always be willing to provide a service effectively so that every job or responsibility given by customers can run well

D. Operational Work

According to (Hasan et al., 2017) Company performance is the result of a management activity in a company. From such performance results presented as a measuring parameter in assessing the success of the management itself, The company's performance is none other than deployed from internal control of the company. The more small companies, Great even medium and flourishing. Some companies are very intense in monitoring how a company's performance progresses as well as its task division and responsibility, The company's performance is something produced by the company within a certain period and refers to a set standard. Companies' performance assessments can be measured by financial and non-finance measures. The size of non-money performance covers customer satisfaction, It's productivity, and cost effectiveness.

According to (Adham, 2019) operational understanding is an abstract concept to facilitate the measurement of a variable. Or operational can be interpreted as a guide in carrying out an activity or research work. Operational definitions according to observed characteristics to define or change concepts which are constructs with words that describe a behavior or observed phenomenon, Tested and determined by others.

According to Hermawan Acepts (2015) in journal quotes (Adham, 2019) Operational understanding is an explanation of how we can measure variables. Such measurements could be done with numbers and specific attributes.

In the journal (Ananto, 2016) operational performance derived from a performance. performance Kind described by 2009 Mangkunegara that term operational performance derived from a job performance or actual performance (work performance or achievement for the) reached by someone in the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carried out in accordance with the responsibilities given. So according to Mangkunegara, 2009 work performance or performance is in quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carried out in accordance with the responsibilities given.

E. Delivery Performance

The journal (. Yudiantmaja et al., 2017) discrimination that is found in all categories is the proportion of third. these aspects said the reliability of delivery is capable of sending " products or services at the promised, not only time, but giving high quality products in a reliable. " But revealed that the appointed time involved in transporting goods, is very important then finch also added " service quality as important as. product quality " The quality of service expressed here refers to a previous statement on punctuality.

According to (Loveri, 2018) Delivery when interpreted into Indonesian is an order delivery or can also be called the delivery of something that has been ordered such as goods etc. Where the delivery of an activity to deliver goods to customers or buyers is sent to a predetermined place.

Thus, delivery performance is a delivery process that is measured in speed (speed) against the specified time, costs incurred in accordance with standards, and how the quality of handling that impacts the trust of the customer is measured in the dimensions that exist in Delivery Performance, namely, time, cost, and quality.

F. Customer Satisfaction

Citations in journals (Fauzi, 2018) according to Kotler, Armstrong, and Opresnik (2017) cited in journals (Fauzi, 2018) state that customer satisfaction is how the quality of the products produced by the company is in accordance with customer expectations. In detail, if the details of the product produced are far from consumer expectations, it means that consumers are not satisfied. If the product matches the customer's expectations, the customer is satisfied. Then if the product quality is more than customer expectations, the customer is satisfied. In addition, customer satisfaction becomes the main goal of companies when they deliver products or services. In addition, customer satisfaction can drive companies to achieve the advantages of customer retention, market share, and profitability (Rust and Zahorik, 1993).

According to (Mardika, 2013) quoted in the journal (Waluyo, 2018) customer satisfaction is a level where the needs, wants, and expectations of customers are met which will result in repeat purchases or continued loyalty. The more quality products and services provided, the higher the satisfaction felt by customers. If customer satisfaction is high, it can cause profits for the business entity.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

According to (sugiyono, 2019) non probability trampling is a technique that does not give the same / opportunity for every element or member of the population to be selected as a sample. The selected non-probability trampling technique is the saturated sampling method of sample determination when all members of the population are used as samples. It's often done when the population is small, Less than 30 employees.

In this research , sample to be retrieved is all employees of ppic pt. export import and warehouse Honda trading aloz 114. employees there A method of sample saturated the sample is a technique used as if all members of the population sample .

V. RESULT

A. Validity Test

The validity of the. 0,184 is critical If the correlation value or r count smaller or less than 0,184 , so the grain. declared invalid On the other hand , if the r count greater than the 0,184. expressed valid and grains.

The following is the result of the (questionnaire) research instruments for every variable treatment:

Table 1: Validity Test Result

Pernyataan	Nilai Koefisien Koreksi (r hitung)				Status
	Kualitas Pelayanan Customer Service (X1)	Kinerja Divisi Operasional (X2)	Performance Delivery (Y)	Kepuasan Customer (Z)	
No. 1	0.811	0.882	0.660	0.877	Valid
No. 2	0.614	0.740	0.951	0.920	Valid
No. 3	0.582	0.812	0.892	0.911	Valid
No. 4	0.607	0.891	0.956	0.830	Valid
No. 5	0.913	0.940	0.907	0.835	Valid
No. 6	0.653	0.891	-	-	Valid
No. 7	0.811	-	-	-	Valid

From: primary data, processed by static package for the social sciences version 25.

Table1 Shows that each item of every variable question Customer Service Quality Export Import PT. Kintetsu Word

Express (X1), Performance of Export Import Operations Division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express (X2), Delivery Performance Container Round Use (Y) and Customer Satisfaction (Z) are all valid.

B. Reliability Test

Table 2: Test Result from Reliability

Variable	Nilai Alpha	Nilai Batas	Status
Kualitas Pelayanan Customer Service (X1)	0.837	0.70	Reliable
Kinerja Divisi Operasional (X2)	0.929	0.70	Reliable
Performance Delivery (Y)	0.926	0.70	Reliable
Kepuasan Customer (Z)	0.923	0.70	Reliable

From: primary data, processed by static package for the social sciences version 25.

Table 2 Shows that the entire alpha value of the question items on each variable is religious, Because the crobach alpha coefficient is greater than 0.70.

From the analysis of validity and reliability, mentioned above overall an item a statement from masing-masing variables can be used and distributed to all respondents, 114 respondents because each item revealed the valid and it is reliable , it will further. analysis was conducted.

C. Partial Test

Table 3: The Partial Test Structure 1

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.232	2.179		2.401	.018
	Kualitas Pelayanan Customer Service	.405	.089	.386	4.556	.000
	Kinerja Divisi Operasional	.379	.105	.306	3.605	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance Delivery

From: primary data, processed by static Package for the Social Sciences version 25

- Quality of Customer Service Export Import PT. Kintetsu Word Express (X1) affects Delivery Performance Container Round Use (Y). The individually (revealed the partial) / obtained the sig. the t Of 0,000 smaller than 0,05 or 0,000 0,05 , so the analysis the significant .Thus , service quality customer service export import pt. servicesKintetsu word express it has some positive effects and significantly to procurement. container shipping the use of performanceThe direct effect service quality customer service delivery indicated to the performance of the beta 0,386 or 38,60. percent

- Performance of Export Import Operations Division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express (X2) affects Delivery Performance Container Round Use (Y). Showing that the test individually (partial) / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.000 smaller than 0.05 or [0.000 < 0.05], then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, the Performance of the Operations Division has a positive and significant effect on the Delivery Performance of Container Round Use. The big influence of the performance of the export import operational division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express for Procurement of Delivery Performance Container Round Use indication by the Beta value of 0.306 or 30.60%.

Table 4: Partial Test Structure 2

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.729	1.496		1.156	.250
	Kualitas Pelayanan Customer Service	.400	.065	.413	6.175	.000
	Kinerja Divisi Operasional	.281	.074	.245	3.770	.000
	Performance Delivery	.317	.064	.343	4.983	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Customer

From: primary data, processed by StaticPackage for the Social Sciences version 25

- Quality of Customer Service Export Import PT. Kintetsu Word Express (X1) affects Customer Satisfaction (Z). Showing that the test individually (partial) / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.000 smaller than 0.05 or [0.000 < 0.05], then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, the Quality of Customer Service Export Import Service PT. Kintetsu Word Express has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. The direct influence of Customer Service Quality Export Import PT. Kintetsu Word Express for Customer Satisfaction shown by a Beta value of 0.413 or 41.30 percent.
- Performance of Export Import Operations Division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express (X2) affects Customer Satisfaction (Z) Shows that the test individually (partial) / t test obtained Sig 0.000 is less than 0.05 or [0.000 < 0.05], then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, the Performance of the Operations Division has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. The big influence of the performance of the export import operational division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express for Customer Satisfaction indicated by a Beta value of 0.245 or 24.50 percent.

- Delivery Performance Container Round Use (Y) affects Customer Satisfaction (Z). Showing the test individually (partial) / t test obtained a Sig value of 0.000 smaller than 0.05 or [0.000 < 0.05], then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, the Delivery Performance Container Round Use has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. The influence of Procurement of Delivery Performance Container Round Use on Customer Satisfaction is indicated by the Beta value of 0.343 or 34.30%.

D. Sobel Test

The sobel test is a test to determine whether a relationship through a mediating variable is significantly able to function as a mediator in the relationship. To make it easier to calculate the z value of the sobel test, you can use the danielsoper application online via www.danielsoper.com with the Statistical Calculator → Mediation Models → Sobel Test Calculator for Significance of Mediation menu, with the following results:

- The Mediation Test of the Effect of Service Quality Customer Service export import PT. Kintetsu Word Express to Customer Satisfaction through Delivery Performance Container Round Use.

Fig. 1: Sobel test model 1

Based on Figure 1 shows a one-tailed probability result of $0.00005703 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the variable Delivery Performance Container Round Use can function as a mediator or able to mediate the indirect

influence of Customer Service Quality Export Import PT. Kintetsu Word Express to Customer Satisfaction.

- The Mediation Test of the Effect of Operational Division Performance on Customer Satisfaction through Performance Delivery.

Fig. 2: Sobel test model 2

Based on Figure 2, showing the results of one-tailed probability of $0.00129089 < 0.05$, so ithe concluded that the variable Delivery Performance Conatiner Round Use Can

serve as a mediator or able to mediate indirect effect of the Performance of the Export Import Operations Division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express to Customer Satisfaction.

E. Goodness of Fittest Test

Table 5: The R Square Sub Structure 1

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.584 ^a	.341	.330	1.047
a. Predictors: (Constant), Kinerja Divisi Operasional , Kualitas Pelayanan Customer Service				

From: primary data, processed by Static Package for the Social Sciences version 25

Table 6: The R Square Sub Structure 2

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.811 ^a	.657	.648	.700
a. Predictors: (Constant), Performance Delivery , Kinerja Divisi Operasional , Kualitas Pelayanan Customer Service				

From: primary data, processed by staticPackage for the Social Sciences version 25.

Then the total variance data can be explained by models measured by:

$$R^2_m = 1 - (1 - R^2_1) \cdot (1 - R^2_2) \cdot (1 - R^2_p) \quad (1)$$

$$R^2_m = 1 - (1 - R^2_1) \cdot (1 - R^2_2) \cdot (1 - R^2_p) \quad (2)$$

$$R^2_m(2) = 1 - (0,341) \times (0,657) \quad (3)$$

$$R^2_m = 0,7760$$

The R^2_m value of 0.7760 means that the diversity of data that can be explained by the model is 77.60 percent, while the remaining 22.40 percent is explained by other variables outside the model. Thus the research model has a high predictive ability of the behavior of the dependent variable which is characterized by a high coefficient of determination above 50 percent.

Fig. 3: The Path Analysis Results Diagram

VI. RESULT OF DISCUSSION

- **H1,** Quality of Customer Service export import export PT. Kintetsu Word Express has a positive and significant effect on Delivery Performance Container Round Use. Based on the results of the analysis, a variable path coefficient of Service Quality Customer Service export import export PT. Kintetsu Word Express against the variable Delivery Performance Container Round Use is 0.386 or 38.60 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the better the Quality of Customer Service Export Import Export Export PT. Kintetsu Word Express then Delivery Performance Container Round Use will be more effective and timely. That way the Delivery Performance Container Round Use needed by the customer, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz can be accepted according to the quantity, quality and time required.
- **H2,** Performance of Export Import Export Operations Division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express has a positive and significant effect on Delivery Performance Container Round Use. Based on the results of the analysis, a variable path coefficient was obtained Performance of the Export Import Export Operational Division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express against the variable Delivery Performance Container Round Use is 0.306 or 30.60 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means that the more effective and efficient the performance of the Export Import Export Operational Division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express then Delivery Performance Container Round Use will be more effective and timely. That way the Delivery Performance Container Round Use needed by the Customer is PT. Honda Trading Aloz Acceptable, according to quantity the quality and the time it takes.
- **H3,** Quality of Customer Service export import export export PT. Kintetsu Word Express It has some positive effects and significantly to customer satisfactionBased

on the results of the analysis obtained a the variable quality of service to customer satisfaction Service export import export PT. Kintetsu Word Express against the Customer Satisfaction variable is 0.413 or 41.30 percent with a significance of 0.000. This means more effectively and efficiently the quality of customer service export import services PT. Kintetsu Word Express then Customer Satisfaction namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz its be more consistent and can be improve. That way Customer Satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz sued PT. Kintetsu Word Express can be achieved well.

- **H4,** Performance of Export Import Export Operations Division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express A positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz. Based on the results of the analysis, a variable path coefficient was obtained Performance of the Export Import Export Operational Division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express to the variable Customer Satisfaction is 0.245 or 24.50% its a significance of 0.000. This means more effectively and efficiently export import operational division performance of PT. Kintetsu Word Express then Customer Satisfaction namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz will be more consistent and can be improved. That way Customer Satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz sued by PT. Kintetsu Word Express can be achieved well.
- **H5,** The performance of shipping the use of container rounds has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz. Based on the results of the analysis , the performance of the delivery of the container round use on variables customer satisfaction is 0.434 or 43.30% its a significance of 0.000. This means that the more effective and efficient the Delivery Performance Container Round Use, the more consistent and improved Customer Satisfaction will be. That way Customer Satisfaction PT.

Honda Trading Aloz sued by PT. Kintetsu Word Express can be achieved well.

- **H6**, Delivery Performance Container Round Use is able to function as a mediator or mediate the effect of Customer Service Quality Export Import PT. Kintetsu Word Express on Customer Satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz. This means that the Delivery Performance of Round Use Containers in accordance with the Quality of Customer Service Export Import PT. Kintetsu Word Express built by the company is able to increase Customer Satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz, so that Delivery Performance Container Round Use as an intervening variable is proven to function to strengthen the influence of the Quality of Customer Service Export Import PT. Kintetsu Word Express on Customer Satisfaction.
- **H7**, Delivery Performance Container Round Use Capable of functioning as a mediator or mediate the operational division export import export performance of PT. Kintetsu Word Express to Customer Satisfaction. This means that the Delivery Performance Container Round Use is in accordance with the Performance of the Export Import Export Operations Division of PT. Kintetsu Word Express built by the company is able to increase Customer Satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz, so that Delivery Performance Container Round Use as variable influence intervening proved serves strengthen export import operational division performance of PT. Kintetsu Word Express to Customer Satisfaction.

VII. THE CONCLUSION

The research and analysis, overall some conclusion can be drawn as follows:

- Quality of Customer Service Export Import PT. Kintetsu Word Express has a positive and significant effect on the Delivery Performance Container Round Use cargo owned by PT. Honda Trading Aloz.
- Export import operational performance of PT. Kintetsu Word Express has a positive and significant effect on the Delivery Performance Container Round Use cargo owned by PT. Honda Trading Aloz.
- Quality of Customer Service Export Import PT. Kintetsu Word Express has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz.
- Export import operational performance of PT. Kintetsu Word Express has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz.
- Delivery Performance Container Round Use cargo owned by PT. Honda Trading Aloz has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz.
- Delivery Performance Container Round Use cargo is able to function as a mediator or mediate indirect influences Quality of Service Customer Service export import PT. Kintetsu Word Express for Customer Satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz.
- Delivery Performance Container Round Use cargo is able to function as a mediator or mediate the indirect

influence of PT. Kintetsu Word Express for Customer Satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz.

VIII. RECOMMENDATION

Based on conclusions on, writer gives advice and recommendations as follows:

- To increase and maintain customer satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz and in order to avoid the company from losses arising from customer distrust which resulted in not using the services of PT. Kintetsu Word Express from Delivery Performance Container Round Use cargo that is not expected by the Customer, then PT. Kintetsu Word Express needs to improve service quality and operational performance in the Delivery Performance Container Round Use process starting from customer requests to cargo to destination in accordance with expectations. This can conclude trust between customers, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz as a user of PT. Kintetsu Word Express in delivery export import cargo owned by PT. Honda Trading Aloz.
- To other researchers who will conduct research on customer service quality, operational performance, delivery performance container round use and customer satisfaction, namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz is advised To examine other variables that also have significant influence. So that hopefully these studies can be useful in giving input and recommendations to companies and academic worlds.

IX. INVOLVEMENT

Based on the results of the study conclusions and recommendations that are outlined above, the implications are that the quality of export import customer service and export import operational performance in container round use delivery performance Getting better, Both formal and non-formal communication can run according to the goal of guiding the company's operating standards, The use of several media communications has been used to smooth the flow of information fast and precise. Tardiness and error in the delivery work round use can be minimized, Although the problem in every process of delivery performance is inevitable, With the quality of customer service import exports and the performance of good import export operations, Whatever issues arise will soon find a solution to avoiding customer distrust., namely PT. Honda Trading Aloz uses the services of PT. Kintetsu Word Express.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Achmad, Bachrudin, H. L. T. (2003). Data Analysis for Survey Research. FMIPA_UNPAD.
- [2]. Adham, M. (2019). Efforts to improve the operational performance of the container terminal of PT Pelindo IV Makassar. *Maritime Journal*, 10(1), 21–35. <http://e-journal.polnes.ac.id/index.php/maritim/article/view/422>
- [3]. Ananto, R. (2016). ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF LEADERSHIP STYLE, MOTIVATION AND WORK DISCIPLINE ON EMPLOYEE

- PERFORMANCE (Empirical Study at PT DHL Global Forwarding Semarang Branch). *Accounting*, 1–73.
- [4]. Donald J. Bowersox. (2006). *Integration of Physical Distribution Management Systems and Material Management*. Earth Literacy.
- [5]. Fandi. (2011). The Influence of the Store Environment on Quality Inferences and Store Image. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 6(11), 951–952., 8–42.
- [6]. Fauzi, A. A. (2018). Electronic Service Quality on Mobile Application of Online Transportation Services. *Jurnal Manajemen Indonesia*, 18(1), 13–27. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jmi.v18i1.1256>
- [7]. Ghozali. (2011). *Application of Multivariate Analysis with SPSS Program*. Diponegoro University.
- [8]. Hasan, H., Darmiasih, I. M. I., & Setyawati, A. (2017). Mustika Alam Lestari Terminal Operational Performance Standards at Tanjung Priok Port. *Journal of Transport and Logistics Business Management*, September 2017, 4(01), 127–134.
- [9]. Kongoti Ayieko, M. (2015). Service Quality Dimensions and Customer Satisfaction in the Kenyan Airline Industry Martin Kongoti Ayieko a Research Project Submitted in Partial fulfillment of the Requirements for the Award of the Degree of Master of Business Administration, School of Bus. November.
- [10]. Kuncoro. (2007). *How to Use and Use Path Analysis*. ALPHABETA.
- [11]. Kusnadi. (2005). Literacy education, philosophy, strategy, implementation,. Directorate of Community Education.
- [12]. Lasse, D. A. (2012). Load management of supply chain activities in the port area. PT. King Grafindo Persada.
- [13]. Lidar, G. (2018). Design of Inbound Information System for Goods Data, Delivery Orders, Pending Goods at Expedition Companies. *Journal of Computer Science and Business*, 9(1), 1869–1878. <https://doi.org/10.47927/jikb.v9i1.121>
- [14]. Loveri, T. (2018). Design of Web-based Tribus brand fertilizer delivery order information system on Cv. Prabu Siliwangi Padang. *Journal J – Click*, 5(1), 98–106.
- [15]. Mardalena, T., & Asmarita, D. (2020). The effect of supervision of loading and unloading goods on operational performance. *Journal of Creative Industries (JIK)*, 3(02), 113–125. <https://doi.org/10.36352/jik.v3i02.28>
- [16]. Meylianti S, B., & Mulia, F. (2009). The effect of the application of JIT (Just In Time) and TQM (Total Quality Management) on Delivery Performance in the automotive industry in Indonesia. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Management| Journal of Theory and Applied Management*, 2(2), 112–127. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jmtt.v2i2.2379>
- [17]. Nakandala, D., Samaranyake, P., & Lau, H. C. W. (2013). A fuzzy-based decision support model for monitoring on-time delivery performance: A textile industry case study. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 225(3), 507–517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2012.10.010>
- [18]. Personal, S., Ayudya, A., & Wulandari, R. S. (2017). Utilization of forklifts for smooth operations in the warehouse of sweetened condensed milk producers. *Journal of Transport and Logistics Business Management*, 3(3), 325–328.
- [19]. Rahmatina, M., Saryadi, & Listyorini, S. (2016). The influence of brand image and perceived quality on customer loyalty through customer satisfaction as an intervening variable (Case study on Garuda Indonesia). *JIAB: Journal of Business Administration Sciences*, 5(1), 300.
- [20]. Rahmayanti, H., Lizana, Y., & Siregar, S. (2016). Analysis of CBU (Completely Built Up) Delivery Service Activities at PT . Indonesia Tanjung Priok Terminal Vehicle. IX, 1–6.
- [21]. Ratnasari, S. (2015). The Effect Of Service Quality And Customer Value On Satisfaction And Its Impact On Customer Trust Pt. Mitra Intertrans Forwarding Palu Branch. *Catalogues*, 3(1), 116–120.
- [22]. Saifuddin Azwar. (2014). *RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY*. Student Library.
- [23]. Subekti, S. (2019). The Effect of Service Quality and Customer Value on Garuda Indonesia Passenger Loyalty at Radin Inten II Airport Lampung. *Transportation Research News*, 31(2), 93–104. <https://doi.org/10.25104/warlit.v31i2.1271>
- [24]. Sugiyono. (2019). *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D RESEARCH METHOD*. ALFABETA.
- [25]. Susilana, R. (2015). *Population and Sample Module*. In *Practicum Module*.
- [26]. Trianto. (2010). *Integrated Learning Model, Concept, Strategy and Implementation in KTSP*. Earth Literacy.
- [27]. Waluyo, M. R. (2018). Analysis of the relationship model of satisfaction and loyalty of online transportation customers. *Tekmapro : Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 13(2), 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.33005/tekmapro.v13i2.41>
- [28]. Winoto, P., Fathoni, A., & Haryono, A. T. (2016). The Influence Of Retailer Performance, Sales Force, And Service Quality On Customer Trust With Word Of Mouth (Wom) As An Intervening Variable At Pt H3I Indonesia. *Journal of Management*, 2(2), 110. <http://jurnal.unpand.ac.id/index.php/MS/article/view/496/482>
- [29]. Yudiantmaja, W. E., Alfiandri, A., & Hidayat, R. (2017). Far from Fire: The service delivery quality gap plaguing Indonesian Ports. *JKAP (Journal of Public Policy and Administration)*, 21(1), 31. <https://doi.org/10.22146/jkap.22713>